

Social Work Referral Readiness: A Study of Staff Awareness and Knowledge in Hospital Settings of Obio Akpor Local Government Area

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Abstract

This study investigated the level of the staff awareness on the cases to be referred to social work professionals in the hospital. Primary source of data was generated through self-administered questionnaires. The population of the study was 800 medical staffs, while the sample size of 267 was determined using the Taro Yamane's formula for sample size determination. The study involved different cadres of hospital staff including; clinicians, nurses, radiologists, dental officers and hospital nutritionist. The result indicated that the majority of respondents which is 78.5% were not aware of the roles and functions of hospital social workers. Moreover, 78.5% of respondents were also not aware of the cases that require social work interventions. The study concludes that these challenges are the source of under-utilization of the medical social workers, which affects the welfare of patients and clients who would otherwise have benefited from social welfare officers interventions. Moreover, the study recommended that the number of social work professionals should be increased so that they can effectively manage patients and clients requiring their care. This is true because the result shows that 81.5% of the respondents agrees that the social work unit has less staffs to handle clients cases. To eliminate these challenges, the study recommends that enough facilities be provided for social workers to carry out their intervention and social workers should be allowed to take decisions within their jurisdiction as these will serve as motivation, thereby bringing job satisfaction.

Introduction

Health care provision in Nigeria is the responsibility of the three tiers of government, with the University Teaching Hospitals and Federal Medical Centres (tertiary health care) being run by the Federal Government, while State Governments manage general hospitals, and Local Government focuses on dispensaries (which are regulated by the federal government through National Primary Health Care Development Agency, or NPHCDA) (Baba M. 2012). Although expenditure on health rose from 12.5 million Nigerian naira in 1970 to 98.2 million in 2008, the healthcare system remains inefficient (Baba M. 2012). After independence in 1962, the Nigerian government was able to use oil revenues and general taxation to fund universal free health care mainly via public facilities (Odeyemi I.A, 2013). However, the global slump in oil prices during the 1980s, coupled with economic and political instability and the general poor state of Nigeria's health services, led to the need to rebuild Nigeria's

health infrastructure (Odeyemi I.A, 2013). In May 1999 the Nigerian government created the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS), with formal enabling of private sector participation to reflect Nigeria's operation of a mixed economy and to correct the previous poor integration of private health facilities (Baba M. 2012). Although the enabling law was signed in 1999, Nigeria's NHIS did not in fact become fully operational until 2005 (Metiboba.S, 2011). One by-product of the psychiatric point of view in social case work is worth consideration in these days of overworked social workers, that is, the greater ease in work that it gives the social worker. The strain of dealing with unknown quantities is perhaps the greatest cause of fatigue in our work. . . . More exact knowledge of personalities with which we are dealing not only saves the worker worry and strain but also releases energy which can be applied to treatment. . . . Another result is that impatience is almost entirely eliminated. No time is wasted upon annoyance or indignation with the uncooperative housewife, the persistent liar, the repeatedly delinquent girl. . . . I know of social workers who looked with suspicion upon the careful preliminary study of personality, because they feared that the entire worker's interest might go into the analysis, and that treatment might be neglected. I believe that fear has been something of a bugaboo in social work. (p. 592)

The implication of Jarrett's address is that a focus on personality allows the social worker to get at the client's problem with ease, thus saving time for treatment. Another possible source of social work's attraction to psychoanalytic theory was Abraham Flexner's 1915 address to the National Conference of Charities and Corrections, in which he said that social work was not a profession. Flexner defined professions as: (a) involving essentially intellectual operations, (b) having large individual responsibility, (c) deriving their raw material from science and learning, (d) working up their material to a practical and definite end, (e) possessing educationally communicable techniques, (f) tending to self-organization, and (g) becoming increasingly altruistic in motivation. He said that although social work had a professional spirit, it failed to meet all of the criteria for a profession because its members did not have a great deal of individual responsibility and lacked a written body of knowledge and educationally communicable techniques. Flexner's address had a profound effect on the field. Some social workers viewed medicine as a model profession and an intrapersonal approach as more professional than one focused on social and environmental factors. Nacman (1990) notes that, by the 1940s, psychosocial information was increasingly being used by medical social workers to make medical diagnoses and treatment plans. This was in contrast to its use, in Ida Cannon's words, "to remove those obstacles, either in the patient's surroundings or in his mental attitude, that interfere with successful treatment, thus freeing the patient to aid in his own recovery" (Cannon 1923.). The work of Helen Harris Perlman countered the tendency to use information primarily to make medical diagnoses and plans by emphasizing social science concepts over psychoanalytic ones and refocusing on society and environment. A focus on environment was reinforced in the 1950s by the community mental health and public health movements and the civil rights movement of the 1960s

Research Aim and Objectives

Investigate the staff awareness on the cases to be referred to social work professionals in the hospital.

Research Questions.

What is the level of the staff awareness on the cases to be referred to social work professionals in the hospital?

Scope of the Study

For the sake of time and limited resources this paper seeks to investigate the challenges facing integration of social work professionals into medical institutions in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study will primarily focus on the health care delivery of medical social welfare department of University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH), as this is part of the Government Teaching Hospital in Obio-Akpor LGA with a functional social work department. Also, the researcher seeks to understand the level of awareness of social work services among health workers.

Significance of the Study

It is also the aim of the researcher to influence government policy through this research paper, therefore this study servers as an eye opener to the happenings in the society some are known while others are unknown by the government officers.

The study is designed to serve as a secondary source of data in social work research; this simply means the study is meant to aid researchers in carrying out their work. The medical practitioners such as the physicians, nurses, psychiatrist seeking to develop their knowledge of the need of the roles social workers in medical setting can also find this study interesting.

Limitations

The research only focused on Government Teaching Hospitals in Obia/Akpor LGA in Rivers State. Hence, the findings may not be adequate in generalizing it to cover other medical institutions. The second factor is that there is a wide geographical scope of Hospitals in Rivers State which was difficult to visit all which may affect conclusion and generalization of findings. Another major limitation is that the respondent of this study are medical workers who have little or no time for activities outside their working schedule. Hence, the retrieval of questionnaire was geatly as only 215 out of 267 questionnaires that were distributed were retrieved.

Definition of Terms

Social Worker

Within the United States, a social worker is an individual who possesses a baccalaureate or master's degree in social work from a school or program accredited by the Council on Social

Work Education. Although all 50 states and the District of Columbia license or certify social workers, licensure and certification laws vary by state. Each social worker should be licensed or certified, as applicable and required, at the level appropriate to her or his scope of practice in the practitioner's jurisdiction(s).

Client

Client refers to the "individual, group, family, or community that seeks or is provided with professional services" (Barker, 2013, p. 73). For purposes of these standards, the term "client" refers to an individual. The term "patient" is more commonly used by social workers employed in health care settings.

Biopsychosocial–Spiritual Perspective

A biopsychosocial–spiritual perspective recognizes the importance of whole person care and takes into account a client's physical or medical condition; emotional or psychological state; socioeconomic, sociocultural, and sociopolitical status; and spiritual needs and concerns.

Bioethics

Bioethics is "the analysis and study of legal, moral, social, and ethical considerations involving the biological and medical sciences" (Barker, 2013).

Case Management

Case management is a collaborative process to plan, seek, advocate for, and monitor services, resources, and supports on behalf of a client. Case management enables a health care social worker to serve clients who may require the services of various health care providers and facilities, community-based organizations, social services agencies, and other programs.

Research Aim and Objectives

- (i) Identify staff awareness on the presence of social work professionals in the hospital

Research Questions

- (i) What is the level of staff awareness on the presence of social work professionals in the hospital?

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functional social work department. Also, the researcher seeks to understand the level of awareness of social work services among health workers.

Significance of the Study

The study aimed at identifying challenges facing integration of social work professionals into medical cadre. The identified challenges shall be communicated to the Ministry of Social Welfare and Rehabilitation Centre and the heads of department to make them understand the existing challenges facing integration of social work professionals into medical practice. The results of this research study can help in developing strategies on how to eliminate those challenges hence maximize the benefits to clients who require social workers interventions. This study will assist to create awareness to the local government authority on the need to strengthen the social welfare department in terms of allocating adequate funds as well as increasing the number of social workers into medical practice. Moreover, on job programs might be designed to orient all staff on the roles and functions of social workers into medical practice including cases required to be attended by social workers.

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Meaning and definition of social work

“Social work practice consists of the professional application of social work values, principles, and techniques to one or more of the following ends: helping people obtain tangible services; counseling and psychotherapy with individuals, families, and groups; helping communities or groups provide or improve social and health services; and

participating in legislative processes. The practice of social work requires knowledge of human development and behavior; of social and economic, and cultural institutions; and of the interaction of all these factors.” –National Association of Social Workers (NASW 2002). “Social workers work with individuals and families to help improve outcomes in their lives. This may be helping to protect vulnerable people from harm or abuse or supporting people to live independently. Social workers support people, act as advocates and direct people to the services they may require. Social workers often work in multi-disciplinary teams alongside health and education professionals.”–British Association of Social Workers (BASW 2019)

Responsibilities of Medical Social Workers and its Uniqueness from Other Social Work Fields

Social work, as a professional domain of social sciences, deals with the systematic treatment and solution of psycho-social problems of individuals, groups and community. Social work has its roots in society to deal with social problems. Hence, it is inclined to achieve two major objectives; the formation of such an environment which assists in making a more satiating system of living and the creation of welfare systems which help the individuals and community to live more creatively and adequately. Medical social work came into being because some doctors and some nurses wanted more far reaching ways of making the sick well and keeping them well. Medical Social Work, a major domain of social work, is also called Hospital Social Work. Medical Social Workers (MSWs) typically work in hospitals and facilitate those patients who need psycho-social assistance. MSWs assess bio-psycho-social and spiritual requirements of the patients and their families and intercede for linking patients and their families to required resources and recuperation in the community; do supportive counseling and psychotherapy of patients to strengthen their social functioning in society. According to Parmar (2014), “Social case work is a process, which develops personality through adjustments consciously affected, individual by individual, between men and their social environment with their problems.” Cobat (2010) defined medical social work as, “a process which serves to assist the case worker in diagnosis and treatment of patient through study of the patient in his social situation and by understanding the patient and his environment. In addition, the medical social work is support by organized sources in making medical treatment more effective.” According to Association of American Medical Colleges (1977), “medical social work is a method which is centered on one to one relationship. It’s a primary technique that supports in social functioning of individuals. The primary function of hospital social work was teaching doctors and nurses about social and psychological aspects of disease and to liaison or act as a bridge between hospital and the social environment and community resources of the patients”. “Case work or medical social work in the hospitals is for ensuring healthy conditions in his or her home in preparation for the patient’s return at home” (Maijor, 2011). Cannon (2010) defined medical social work as, “Hospital social worker’s role includes the direct treatment of the patient’s social and psychological problems which were among the causes or effects of their health problems or which acted as barriers to cooperation with the medical treatment plan”. “A Medical Social Worker is a social worker who works in a

medical setting such as a hospice, outpatient clinic, hospital, community health agency, or long-term care facility. MSWs are most often referred as “social workers,” and sporadically may have other titles, such as Case/Care Manager.” (Morrow, 2014). Many types of patients could benefit from the care of a MSW. Specifically, individuals with mental illness; homeless individuals; the terminally ill; transplant patients; individuals with chronic degenerative illnesses; and individuals with numerous emotional, financial, social or housing problems. Medical social work is a unique field of social work practice that is accompanied with varied responsibilities carried out in the hospital and medical center setting. Medical social workers assist patients and their families in understanding a patient’s ailment and they provide patients with counseling regarding decisions that need to be made as well as go through the emotions patients and families may experience due to the diagnosis of a patient (Whitaker, 2006). Medical social workers work in fast-paced environments and are part of interdisciplinary teams which involves working closely with physicians, nurses, and other health professionals. Medical social workers are vital to the interdisciplinary team as they offer the “person-in-environment” perspective (Whitaker, 2006). It is clear that physicians and nurses value medical social workers in their interdisciplinary teams (Zimmerman & Dabelko, 2007). Keefe, Geron, and Enguidanos (2009) study found that overall primary care clinicians believe that social workers are able to improve their ability to deliver comprehensive quality care to their patients. In addition, Nurses have stated that social workers fill in needed roles and are seen as nurse “extenders”. Both physicians and nurses agree that medical social workers fill in the necessary gaps needed in providing patients with better care which they feel will ultimately result in more satisfied members (Keefe, Geron, & Enguidanos, 2009).

Being a member of a multi-disciplinary healthcare squad, the MSW provides mediations to facilitate patients during recovery process and their families in adjusting to grave and protracted medical conditions. The recovery of patient and his life’s quality depends on his ability and his family’s will to adjust and cope with the effect of medical conditions and subsequent infirmity on their finances, relationships, employment and lifestyle. They support patients and their families to understand to manage life emergencies resulting from chronic or acute medical situations, and emphasize on improving their physical and mental comfort to attain self-confidence. They also assist in reducing the liability of patients and their families from sustained healthcare and social expenses. MSWs succor patients and their families regarding health-related glitches and trepidations. They perform complete assessment of a patient’s financial, emotional, social and environmental support requirements and intimate other health-care team members about these aspects, which may have an impact on the patient’s well-being and health. They work with the patient’s support systems or family along with other agencies to make a plan for patient’s care in his house. The most important role played by MSWs is patient’s counseling. MSWs assist patients decide about appropriate health-care and other health services, initiate support group discussions, provide support to

patients with severe or protracted illnesses and provide individual counseling. MSWs effectively coordinate patient's discharge planning in hospital settings. They facilitate patients and their families in making arrangements for in-home medical equipment, accessing in-home health-care services, coordinating follow-up treatments, providing transportation and referring patients to social service agencies working in the community. They are every so often assisting patients in health insurance coverage and accessing financial support. In some cases, they also closely work with health insurance companies to decide about the patient's remunerations and support for the patient. The basic functions of MSWs (Parmar, 2014) are;

- Psycho-social, physical and spiritual assessment for determining the resilience and strength of the patients, their families and community support systems to assist the people function within the society.
- Educating the patient's family on bio-psycho-social requirements of the patients and how they can acquire resources; and mediating familial skirmishes.
- Counseling patients and their families.
- Risk assessment of patients (self-harm like suicide or others such as child abuse, family violence).
- Funds management and providing financial assistance to deserving cases.
- Discharge planning of patients.
- Referring services for associating patients to available community resources.

Research Method

The Study Area

The study was conducted at University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH) Port Harcourt. The area is selected as one of the government hospitals with social work professionals working with other medical field practitioners.

Research Design

Nachimias (2003) defined research design as "the blue print that enables the investigators to come up with solutions to problems and guide him/her in the various stages of the research. This study adopts a descriptive cross sectional survey. Cross-sectional surveys are studies aimed at determining the frequency or level of a particular attribute in a defined population at a particular point in time. A cross sectional study is commonly used in medical and social science researches. A cross sectional study or prevalence study is the type of observational study that involves the analysis of data collected from a population or representative subset at one specific point in time. The data were collected using questionnaires which were given to respondents and the analysis of the collected data portrayed the factors that challenge integration of social work professionals in medical services.

Population of the Study

According to Nachimias (2003) population is defined as “the aggregate of all cases that conform to some designated set of specification. Kombo and Tromp (2006) defined population as the largest group from which the sample is taken. The population of the study comprises all the medical staffs of the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital working with social welfare department in the hospital which is about 800 in number. This number was obtained from the human resource department of the hospital.

Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

Nachimias (2003) defined sample as “the sub set of a population”. Thus, in view of the fact that our study involves a finite population, a sample size that can be possibly reached is obtained. Kothari (2004) defined sampling techniques or procedure as “a definite plan for obtaining a sample for population given. The study sample size was arrived at using the Taro Yamen’s 1970 formula.

The sample size was calculated by using the Taro Yamen Sample size determination formula;

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Whereby; n=Sample size, N= total population (800) and e= an acceptable error (0.05).

$$\text{Therefore } n = \frac{800}{1+800(0.05)^2} = 266.7$$

In this research study the sample size was 267.

Data Collection Method

Questionnaire

The questionnaire involves a set of questions to collect information from subjects on their perceptions, feelings to the subject under study. It helps in providing accurate data that are quantifiable easily. The study which is dominantly quantitative in nature, adopts the structured questionnaire in the generation of primary data for the study. Copies of questionnaire would be personally administered, followed up and retrieved.

Data Analysis Approach

Braun and Clarke (2006) state that “thematic analysis is a qualitative analytic method for identifying, analyzing and reporting patterns within data. Thematic analysis minimally organizes and described data set in details. However, it goes further than this and interprets various aspect of the research topic. Data collected from the field were structured to ensure consistency of responses. Data generated were arranged and coded according to themes and then fed into the data editor section of Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS 21.0). Analysis were undertaken in two phases beginning with the demographic profile, using percentages, describes the frequencies of responses to various sample characteristics.

Secondly the research questions and findings were analyzed through mean scores and standard deviations

Validity of the Instrument

According to Babbie (2007), the term validity refers to the extent to which an empirical measure adequately reflects the real meaning of the concept under consideration. Validity is defined as the ability of the scale to measure what it is designed or purported to measure. For validity of the measurement to be established, there should be a complete absence of measurement error. It is important that a reliability and validity test be carried out comprehensively at every stage of the research work. Babbie (2007) posit that, after operationalizing, defining variables and applying different scaling techniques, it is pertinent to ensure that each research instrument employed be adequately tested for reliability and validity. In this study, the researcher ensured that the measure for reliability included an adequate and effective representative set of items that tap the concept. Serious effort was made to ensure that the scale items represented the domain or universe of the concept being measured. In other words, the measurement is a function of how well the dimensions and indicators of the various concepts are been delineated, which logically reflected the study variables. The validation of the instrument would be ensured through my supervisors vetting. Through this process, errors in the questionnaire such as ambiguity, contradictory questions, poor wording of questions, misleading or poor instructions among others would be detected and eliminated.

Tests of Reliability of Instrument

Reliability is the ability of a measuring instrument to achieve consistent results each time it is adopted. However, Nunnally (1979) asserts that the reliability alpha values in determining the internal consistency of the instrument should maintain a minimum threshold of 0.7. Based on this, the Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient method was utilized in this study since it is the most predominant method of testing reliability in social sciences research (Hair, Black, Babin & Anderson 2010).

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion Of Findings

Table 1 Job Statues of Respondents

	Frequenc y	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	169	82.4	82.4	82.4
Valid Yes	36	17.6	17.6	100.0
Total	205	100.0	100.0	

Source: Research Survey Data, 2019

Figure 1: bar chart showing part time distribution of respondents

From the data in table 1, it can be observed that 166 representing 81 percent of the respondents are not part full time staffs while 39 respondents representing 19 percent are part time staffs. The result simply shows that the hospital has more full time staffs than part time staff.

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question:

What is the level of the staff awareness on the cases to be referred to social work professionals in the hospital?

Table 2: Responses Rate of Staff Awareness on the Cases to Be Referred to Social Work Professionals in the Hospital.

	Staff awareness on the cases to be referred to social work professionals	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Std.
1	I understand cases handled by social workers in the hospital	25	19	16	64	81	2.23	1.37691
2	I understand when patients should be referred to Social workers	29	19	9	95	53	2.40	1.34127
3	In the hospital Social workers mediates and advocate for the rights of the patients	28	24	18	24	110	2.38	2.50325
4	Social workers are called upon in the hospital to handle the case of indigent patients	26	28	13	74	64	2.40	1.38159

5	Social workers resolve disputes that may lead to depression and escalate patients illness	24	19	17	109	36	2.44	1.22195
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Source: Research Survey Data, 2019

The result of table 2 reveals that all items (1-5) have mean scores below 2.50. The statement ‘I understand cases handled by social workers in the hospital’ has the lowest mean score (M=2.23; SD=1.37691) followed by ‘In the hospital Social workers mediates and advocate for the rights of the patients’ (M=2.38; SD= 2.50325), ‘I understand when patients should be referred to Social workers’ (M=2.40;SD=1.34127), ‘Social workers are called upon in the hospital to handle the case of indigent patients’ (M=2.40;SD=1.38159), ‘Social workers resolve disputes that may lead to depression and escalate patients illness’ (M=2.44;SD=1.22195). These shows all the items indicate that medical staffs are not aware of the cases that require the social workers attention in the hospital. This is true since the mean values are below the benchmark of 2.5, meaning that most of the respondents were on the disagree range of the scale. Thus it is clear that medical staffs are not aware that social workers are called upon in the cases of indecency, mediation and resolving of dispute among patients and family that may lead to the escalation of patient’s illness.

Discussion of findings

72% of the respondent agree to the fact the social work unit in the hospital is understaffed, 60% of the respondent agree that social workers in the hospital have less time and more work load, 55% of the respondent agree that social workers in the hospital are not allowed to take decision affecting their own profession, 75% of the respondent agree that social workers in the hospital have less resources to carry out their intervention in the hospital, while 75% also agree that social workers are provided with less facilities to carry out their duty in the hospital. These result shows that social workers in the hospital are facing serious challenges which need urgent attention of both the ministry of health and the ministry of social welfare and rehabilitation. Hence it is the desire of the researcher to unveil these challenges as it seriously affects the well-being of patients in the hospital. Secondly, the result also shows that social work intervention is facing a lot of limitation in the government hospitals in Rivers state, and apart from lack of awareness of roles and cases that need social work intervention, this noble profession is facing other challenge which are unknown to the public. The result further indicates that only few of medical staff are aware of cases that required social workers’ intervention (21.5%). This is the result of inadequate knowledge on the part of medical staff on the roles and functions of hospital social workers. The implication of this result is that only few or even no cases would be referred to hospital social work professionals as shown to the conceptual frame work.

Recommendations

- i. Hospital social workers should not work in isolation therefore they have to work with hospital staff daily.
- ii. The hospital social workers should be given adequate funds in each fiscal year to enhance smooth running of their daily activities.

- iii. The hospital social workers should conduct daily ward visits in order to identify patients who need their help rather than wait for them to be called

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